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Report of TWG Robotics: **Landscape of Robotics Standards**

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■ Foreword

As Europe strives towards its Digital Decade targets for 2030, robotics is set to play a pivotal role in transforming key sectors like manufacturing, healthcare, and mobility.

Robotics represents a core enabler of Europe's broader industrial and digital transformation strategies and the integration of robotics within smart cities, hospitals, and manufacturing ecosystems demands comprehensive and forward-looking standards that ensure safety, interoperability, and regulatory compliance.

This report produced by the StandICT.eu Technical Working Group (TWG) on robotics provides an updated overview of standards for three critical robotics applications: Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs), ICT Networks, and Medical Robotics. These areas have strategic importance but are also affected by several standardisation gaps. As Europe advances in these sectors, the need for harmonised standards becomes ever more pressing to safeguard citizens, foster innovation, and strengthen Europe's competitiveness in the global market.

A central focus of the current landscape revolves around safety standards, driven by forthcoming EU regulations such as the **Machinery Regulation** and the **AI Act**. These frameworks reflect Europe's commitment to building trust in emerging technologies by ensuring that robotics systems are not only efficient but also safe and ethical. In particular, the intersection between robotics and ICT networks is of high relevance, as we see the rise of autonomous systems, driven by artificial intelligence and machine learning, transforming traditional network models into self-managing ecosystems.

To harness the potential of robotics, Europe should align its efforts on standardisation with its broader digital and green transition goals. Investments in research, development, and innovation shall be matched by the creation of standards that foster cross-sector interoperability, while also addressing key challenges such as cybersecurity, data protection, and the ethical deployment of AI-powered systems.

This report also provides some support to European actors, including SMEs, in navigating the complex world of robotics standards. Beyond the collection of standards here reported, however, the development of guidelines and training programs will be crucial in empowering smaller companies to adopt and benefit from these technologies without facing overwhelming costs or administrative burdens.

At a policy level, initiatives such as the European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge, and Cloud, and the AI, Data, and Robotics Partnership are instrumental in shaping the future landscape of robotics standardisation.

By aligning standardisation efforts with Europe's digital transformation goals, robotics can play a key role in fostering innovation, boosting competitiveness, and contributing to sustainable, resilient solutions across critical sectors such as healthcare, manufacturing, and mobility.

The StandICT.eu 2026 Consortium

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■ Introduction

This Landscape Report provides a good overview on standards and ongoing standardization activities in the areas of Robotics, Robotics and Autonomous Systems (RAS), and Autonomic / Autonomous Networks (ANs) as closely linked areas, in various industry Standards Development Organizations (SDOs) and Fora as presented in this report. This is due to the fact that there are shared commonalities in certain standardization requirements and certain standards that can commonly be applicable across Autonomic/Autonomous Networking (ANs) and Robotics and Autonomous Systems (RAS). The report also highlights some gaps in standards that need to be closed as the industries that implement or use technologies and products in these closely linked areas continue their developments into the future. On the other hand, the report gives a good overview picture to experts working in the areas of Robotics, RAS, and ANs concerning the commonalities, standards and gaps that need to be addressed as we move into the future. An example of the case of shared commonalities in certain standardization requirements and certain standards that can commonly be applicable across ANs and RAS pertains to the need for a standard for **Common Operational Principles of Autonomic/Autonomous Networks (COPAAN) Blueprint** (discussed in this report document) that should be produced based inputs from various domains, including robotics, autopilot used in aircrafts, and other domains. It is believed that the COPAAN blueprint's specifications would be applicable to ICT class of ANs, certain kinds of robots, self-driving vehicles, and other domains, as it pertains to *Governance and Federation Interfaces* required of self-managing systems like ANs. The IEEE INGR Future Networks Initiative that is addressing the COPAAN topic and is compiling a White Paper on the topic has put forward the requirement for a funded project (e.g., public funded project) as a neutral instrument that could work on the COPAAN specifications.

The area of robotics continues to grow immensely due to the continuous advancements in application areas such as digital transformation, smart cities, ICT networks for intelligent connectivity services for smart city and smart government use cases, smart office, smart home, smart living, and other emerging application areas for robotics. The other perspective pertaining to the drivers for the witnessed growth in the area of robotics is that RAS for intelligent (smart) manufacturing, smart factories, and digital continuity and for non-industrial use cases too are trends influencing the growth in the area of robotics. With the growth trends in robotics, RAS and ANs developments, comes the need to accelerate the development of the applicable standards to close any standards gaps that exist in these interlinked areas. While gaps in standards for robotics are being addressed, there are indications that more gaps need to be studied and closed as discussed in this report, e.g., in the aspects of “*Knowledge, Tasks and Maps Representations for Robotics*” and “*Functional Safety for Robotics*”.

Autonomic/Autonomous Networking (ANs) and Robotics and Autonomous Systems (RAS): shared commonalities in certain standardization requirements

The vision of *Autonomic and Autonomous Networks (ANs)* (defined in ETSI White Paper No. 56 [6], [TM Forum IG1218] and [2][3][7]) in general, mainly covers systems and ICT networks that are characterized, individually and collaboratively within certain scopes/boundaries, as smart and intelligent (with some degree of cognitive capabilities, i.e., with learning and reasoning capabilities). They exhibit so-called **self-* behavioral attributes/features** such as *auto-discovery of resources, information, context-changes or operational environment and state to perform self-configuration; self-diagnosis; self-repair; self-optimization; self-protection; self-defense; self-healing; self-awareness, self-organization; self-adaption; etc.* The characterization of such systems is often described as self-managing systems (includes self-organizing systems), and *Autonomous Networks (ANs)* fall under the umbrella of such systems.

Why are there emerging extensions on the early scope of ANs (going beyond traditional ICT networks)? Because it turns out there are commonalities across various classes of ANs and there may even be developed industry standards that can be shared across diverse classes of ANs implementations. Also, the diversification of the classes of ANs enables the potential for innovations and federations among ANs that belong to different classes of ANs as industries and societies move into the future, e.g., in the case of the vision of what IEEE has termed *symbiotic autonomous systems* (which include a lot of use cases on **Human-Machine** interactions).

The quest for smart and intelligent cognitive systems that are powered by closed control-loops for the autonomics paradigm, cognition (learning and reasoning) enablers, Artificial Intelligence (AI) Models/Algorithms and Computational Intelligence, is increasingly on the sharp rise in various industry sectors. In sectors such as traditional ICT networks (e.g., Access Networks, Transport and Core Networks, Data Center (DC) Networks, IT enterprise networks and environments) that serve for service consumptions by humans (e.g., voice, video, and data call services); Manufacturing; Automotive; Aerospace; Healthcare; Mining; and many other industry sectors. In ICT networks (public and enterprise private networks), the need for network automation and related standards has continued to grow, mainly because it is becoming increasingly very difficult to manage the increasingly complex networks and technologies using traditional manual management of networks by humans. For ICT Network Operators (CSPs) who operate the evolving and future networks such as 4G, 5G and Beyond networks, there is need for a shift to the way ICT networks are designed and operated. A shift to a new way that brings about OPEX sustainability in operating networks and services and enables operators and enterprises to innovate and deliver services to consumers in a richly agile manner—thanks to self-managed (intelligent) networks. Hence, there has been huge efforts recently launched in various SDOs/Fora in producing Standards for Cognitive/Autonomic Management and Control (AMC) of ICT Networks and Services—powered by Control-Loops for Autonomics, Artificial Intelligence (AI) Models/Algorithms and Computational Intelligence. Systems at various levels of abstractions within the various industry sectors, ranging from Network Elements/Functions of ICT infrastructures and associated Management and Control Systems/Platforms of the ICT infrastructures that serve consumer devices and services delivered for human consumptions (e.g., voice, video and data communication services); Industrial Robots in the Manufacturing sector; Service Robots; Robots or ICT systems used in healthcare and other sectors; elements or systems in the scope of Internet of Things (IoT), and in other scopes; should be designed to incorporate Control-Loops for Autonomics, Cognition, Artificial Intelligence (AI) Models/Algorithms and Computational Intelligence at varying degrees of complexity. Such design principles for the various systems shall enable the systems (individually and collaboratively within certain scopes/boundaries) to be smart and intelligent (cognitive, with learning and reasoning capabilities) and exhibit the so-called Self-* behavioral attributes/features such as *Auto-Discovery of Resources, Information, Context-changes or*

environments; Self-Configuration; Self-Diagnosis; Self-Repair; Self-Optimization; Self-Protection; Self-Defense; Self-Healing; Self-Aware, Self-Organizing; Self-Adapting; etc. The characterization of such systems is often described as Self-Managing Systems (includes Self-Organizing Systems).

This means there are certain types of design principles and operational principles of smart/intelligent (cognitive) systems that are commonly shared across the various AN based systems and across industry sectors. Design principles that include Bio-Inspired designs (e.g., borrowing from the concept of the human body's Autonomic Nervous System (ANS) to design and incorporate Control-Loops for Autonomics into systems), and use of Cognition, Artificial Intelligence (AI) Models/Algorithms and Computational Intelligence, are shared across various intelligent/cognitive systems. Operational principles for such kinds of smart/intelligent (cognitive) systems may be shared among certain classes of smart/intelligent (cognitive) systems, and there may be common operational principles that are applicable for all such systems. One of the commonalities among the systems, with respect to design principles and operational principles is that of the embedding of *Control-Loop(s) Structures* into their designs to mimic the control-loop(s) design and functionality of the Autonomic Nervous System (ANS) of a human body. [4] [5] present and discuss the taxonomical relationships between an "Autonomic Network" and an "Autonomous Network", and how the concept of autonomicity (autonomics) is an enabler for achieving autonomous network property and behaviour.

The industry has classified the various systems and related initiatives in Standardization under the general umbrella of the so-called Autonomic/Autonomous Networks (ANs). Under the umbrella of ANs we find smart/intelligent (cognitive) systems in the scope of traditional ICT networks (e.g., Access Networks, Transport and Core Networks, Data Center Networks, IT enterprise networks and environments) that serve for service consumptions by humans (e.g., voice, video and data call services); as well as smart/intelligent (cognitive) systems in the scope of Machine-to-Machine or IoT Systems; smart/intelligent (cognitive) systems in the scope Industrial Robots or Service Robots; smart/intelligent (cognitive) systems in the scope Autonomous/Self-Driving Vehicles; smart/intelligent (cognitive) systems in the scope of Drones; smart/intelligent (cognitive) systems in the scope of other sectors. In some SDOs/Fora, there are other classifications such as Robotics and Autonomous Systems (RAS) classifications in ETSI White Paper No. 45. Some initiatives keep the classification of Autonomous Networks to ICT networks only. While other related work in other various SDOs/Fora has focused on Autonomic Networks (and interchangeably called Autonomous Networks too) as a classification, but mostly in the scope of traditional ICT networks (e.g., Access Networks, Transport and Core Networks, Data Center Networks, IT enterprise networks and environments) the serve for service consumptions by humans (e.g., voice, video, and data call services). There is a lot of AN related work in ETSI, IEEE, ITU-T, BBF, TM Forum, 3GPP, and in other SDOs/Fora. ETSI has recently published the Generic Autonomic Networking Architecture (GANA) Standard (ETSI TS 103 195-2), an Architectural Reference Model for Autonomic Networking, Cognitive Networking and Self-Management of Networks and Services in which Control-Loops, Cognition, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Computational Intelligence play a role in Autonomic Management and Control (AMC) of ICT networks and services [1]. The GANA Model is being instantiated into various network architectures and their associated management and control architectures and has been adopted by many SDOs/Fora in embedding autonomicity in their architectures as illustrated on **Figure 1**. As described in [1] [3] [4] [R5] the ETSI GANA ushers in the era of the so-called *GANA Knowledge Planes (KPs) Driven Networking* now and into the future. A GANA KP Platform shall drive *self-* operations for AMC such as self-adaptation, self-optimization, self-monitoring, self-protection and self-defense, and other self-* objectives* for the network and services within a certain scope and shall federate with other GANA KPs responsible for other network scopes and domains so that the federated GANA KPs drive collaborative AMC operations across domains.

Recently a so-called Multi-SDO Initiative was created in 2021 on Autonomous Networks (ANs) that covers the general broad umbrella of Autonomic/Autonomous Networks (ANs), and the Multi-SDO initiative on ANs (dubbed "Multi SDO Autonomous Network coordination") is hosted by TM Forum. The Multi-SDO Initiative under the auspices of the TM Forum has identified a new Industry Standardization Requirement that needs to be addressed urgently by the industry for the benefit of operating smart/intelligent (cognitive) systems of various classes across various sectors. Therefore, what is immediately needed is the development of a so-called standardized Blueprint of Common Operational Principles for Autonomic/Autonomous Networks (COPAAN). **Figure 2** illustrates a potential solution for implementing this required COPAAN blueprint standard. Certain types of robots and other classes of ANs need to be governed by humans through Common Operational Principles (COPAAN) such that their behaviour is governed and constrained by humans and not go out of control and cause harm. ANs shall be governable by humans through, e.g., *goals, objectives, intents or policies* humans shall provide as input to govern an AN. [3] presents the *Draft of a Conceptual Model of an AN's Key Operations-related Peripheral Interfaces* for derivation of COPAAN, namely the "Governance Interface" and "Federation Interface", *Primitives an Actors on the Interfaces*.

Figure 1: Historical Background on Standardization Efforts for Autonomic/Autonomous Networking Frameworks for ICT networks, and Ecosystem on ETSI Collaboration with other SDOs/Fora on the Topic [NOTE: Extract from [2]]

Multi-SDO initiative on ANs is meant to facilitate for information exchange among SDOs/Fora through coordination to enable to reduce duplication work, avoid standards collisions across SDOs/Fora, and identify gaps that need to be closed in standardization on ANs. The SDOs/Fora and Open Source involved in the multi-SDO include ETSI, GSMA, ONAP, NGMN, 3GPP SA5, CCSA, IEEE, IETF, ITU-T.

Figure 2: Proposal on “How to Build the Blueprint (COPAAN), the kinds of Inputs required for Developing the COPAAN, and the Outputs that should then be consumed by SDOs/Fora working on ANs” [NOTE: Extracted from [2][3]]

A Proposal (see **Figure 3**) has been made in Multi-SDO initiative for “A Call for a Project to work on Producing the **Common Operational Principles of Autonomic/Autonomous Networks (COPAAN)** Blueprint such that the Project can then work with any suitable SDO/Forum that can standardize the Blueprint and play the role of evolving and maintaining it” [3].

Figure 3: Proposal on “Call for a Project to work on Producing the COPAAN Blueprint such that the Project can then work with any suitable SDO/Forum that can standardize the Blueprint and play the role of evolving and maintaining it” [NOTE: Extracted from IEEE [3]]

Landscape of Standards

ANSI/CAN/UL

Title: Automated Mobile Platforms (AMPs)

Abstract: These requirements cover battery-operated mobile platforms with or without a payload. These devices are intended to be used indoors only or as outdoor use devices in a commercial or industrial environment. The device is battery powered using either lead acid batteries or lithium based batteries that, if rechargeable, are charged through a conductive system

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://webstore.ansi.org/Standards/UL/UL3100Ed2021>

Published: Q2 2021

ANSI/RIA

Title: Industrial Mobile Robots - Safety Requirements - Part 1: Requirements For The Industrial Mobile Robot

Abstract: Specifies safety requirements for industrial mobile robots (IMRs). It describes basic hazards associated with IMRs in an industrial environment (See Clause 3.12), and provides requirements to eliminate or adequately reduce, the risks associated with these hazards.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: https://webstore.ansi.org/Standards/RIA/ANSIRIAR15082020?msclkid=7078803ecc491e7bff59e2bd9c0a44ad&utm_source=bing&utm_medium=cpc&utm_campaign=Campaign%20%2330%20GB&utm_term=ANSI%20RIA%20R15.08-1-2020&utm_content=RIA

Published: Q4 2020

ASME

Title: MUS STANDARDS COMMITTEE ON MOBILE UNMANNED SYSTEMS

Abstract: Establish standards and guidelines that provide safe and reliable application of Mobile Unmanned Systems (MUS) for unmanned aerial systems (UAS), ground/crawlers and submersibles to inspect, monitor, and maintain industrial facilities and power plants as well as equipment, transmission lines, and pipelines.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://cstools.asme.org/csconnect/CommitteePages.cfm?Committee=102534755>

Published: Q2-2022

Title: Standard Practice for Describing Stationary Obstacles Utilized within A-UGV Test Methods

Abstract: This practice specifies physical characteristics that can be used to describe obstacles utilized within ASTM Committee F45 test methods. The obstacle characteristics specified in this practice are not described with respect to the manner in which they will be sensed or detected by an A-UGV. Rather, the obstacles are described according to their real world characteristics.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.astm.org/f3381-19.html>

Published: Q4 2019

Title: Standard Guide for A-UGV Capabilities

Abstract: This guide categorizes the autonomous capabilities of an automatic through autonomous-unmanned ground vehicle (A-UGV) based on a list of eleven capability categories.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.astm.org/f3470-20.html>

 Published: Q3 2020

Title: Standard Test Method for Grid-Video Obstacle Measurement

Abstract: This test method measures an automatic/automated/autonomous-unmanned ground vehicle (A-UGV) kinetic energy reduction when objects appear in the A-UGV path and within the stop-detect range of the vehicle safety sensors in situations in which the desired reaction is for the vehicle to stop as opposed to avoiding the obstacle by traveling on an alternative path.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.astm.org/f3265-17.html>

 Published: Q3 2017

Title: Standard Practice for Implementing Communications Impairments on A-UGV Systems

Abstract: This practice considers impairments of communications within an automatic, automated, or autonomous unmanned ground vehicle (AUGV) system during task execution. An A-UGV system typically uses communications between an A-UGV and fixed system components and resources, such as off-board control, job and fleet scheduling, infrastructure equipment interactions, or cloud-computing programs for tasks.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.astm.org/f3243-21.html>

 Published: Q1 2021

Title: Standard Terminology for Driverless Automatic Guided Industrial Vehicles

Abstract: This terminology covers terms associated with unmanned (that is, driverless), ground (that is, land-based and in continuous contact with the ground), industrial vehicles. By providing a common and consistent lexicon, the purpose of this terminology is to facilitate communication between individuals who may be involved in the research, design, deployment, and use of unmanned ground vehicles, including but not limited to, for manufacturing, distribution, security, etc. The terminology covers terms used in performance test methods of automatic guided vehicles (AGVs), autonomous mobile robots, and all other driverless, ground vehicles. In addition, with increasingly intelligent vehicle systems with onboard equipment, robotics industry terms that are used in associated test methods and descriptions are also included.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.astm.org/catalogsearch/result?q=F3200-20A>

 Published: Q1 2020

CEN TC 150 WG 3

Title: SAFETY OF INDUSTRIAL TRUCKS - DRIVERLESS TRUCKS AND THEIR SYSTEMS

Abstract: Pertains to all trucks and their systems except: a) trucks solely guided by mechanical means (rails, guides, etc); b) trucks operating in areas open to persons unaware of the hazards.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: https://shop.standards.ie/en-ie/standards/en-1525-1997-345607_saig_cen_cen_790527/

 Published: Q3 1997

Title: Test Mobile Platform to Maintain a Separation Distance

Abstract: The purpose of this protocol is to validate the safety skill “maintain safe distance” by measurement. Its scope is limited to mobile robot systems that used in Logistics and Manufacturing applications. In this context, the skill “maintain safe distance” is often used to protect workers from injuries caused by collisions where the mobile robot collides with a part of the human. The protocol validates that the stopping time or distance is never exceeded in a mobile robot system when using a safety skill that detect objects and triggers a stop. The validation of this protocol requires that the reader has a distance measuring system available.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: <https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/MOB-MSD-1%20Test%20Mobile%20Platform%20to%20Maintain%20a%20Separation%20Distance.pdf>

Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test Mobile Robot Arm for Collision with Fixed Object (Crush)

Abstract: The purpose of this protocol is to validate the safety skill “limit interaction energy” by measurement. Its scope is limited to mobile robot arms that used in Logistics and Manufacturing applications. In this context, the skill “limit interaction energy” is often used to protect workers from injuries caused by collisions where the mobile robot arm traps a part of the human body against a fixed obstacle. The validation of this protocol requires that the reader has a bio-fidel force and pressure measurement device available.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: [https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/MRO-LIE-1%20Test%20Mobile%20Robot%20Arm%20for%20Collision%20with%20Fixed%20Object%20\(Crush\).pdf](https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/MRO-LIE-1%20Test%20Mobile%20Robot%20Arm%20for%20Collision%20with%20Fixed%20Object%20(Crush).pdf)

Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test mobile platform to limit the range of motion

Abstract: The purpose of this protocol is to validate the skill “limit range of motion” for industrial mobile robots and their payload. In this context, the skill limit range of motion is used to avoid the mobile robot and its payload to go through a forbidden space location. The validation protocol is aimed to check whether the footprint of the system is correctly set or not.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: <https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/MOB-LRM-1%20Test%20Mobile%20Platform%20for%20Limit%20the%20Range%20of%20Motion%202021-09-28.pdf>

Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test Mobile Platform to Maintain a Separation Distance

Abstract: The purpose of this protocol is to validate the safety skill “maintain safe distance” by measurement. Its scope is limited to Highly Automated Agricultural Machines (HAAM). In this context, the skill “maintain safe distance” is often used to protect workers from injuries caused by collisions where the HAAM collides with a part of the human. The protocol validates that the stopping distance is never exceeded in a HAAM system when using a safety skill that detect objects and triggers a stop. The validation of this protocol requires that the reader has a distance measuring system available.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: <https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/MOB-MSD-2%20Test%20Mobile%20Platform%20to%20Maintain%20a%20Separation%20Distance.pdf>

Published: Q4 2021

IEC TC 65 SC 65A

Title: Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems.

Abstract: The standard covers safety-related systems that incorporate electrical/electronic / programmable electronic devices.

The standard specifically covers hazards that occur when safety functions fail. And the main goal of the safety standard is to reduce the risk of failure to a tolerable level.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://webstore.iec.ch/publication/5515>

 Published: Q2 2010

ISO TC 110 SC 2

Title: Industrial trucks — Safety requirements and verification — Part 4: Driverless industrial trucks and their systems

Abstract: This document specifies safety requirements and the means for their verification for driverless industrial trucks (hereafter referred to as trucks) and their systems.

Examples of driverless industrial trucks (trucks of ISO 5053-1) can also be known as: “automated guided vehicle”, “autonomous mobile robot”, “bots”, “automated guided cart”, “tunnel tugger”, “under cart”, etc.

This document also contains requirements for driverless industrial trucks which are provided with:

- ▷ — automatic modes which either require operators' action(s) to initiate or enable such automatic operations;
- ▷ the capability to transport one or more riders (which are neither considered as drivers nor as operators);
- ▷ additional manual modes which allow operators to operate the truck manually; or
- ▷ a maintenance mode which allows manual operation of truck functions for maintenance reasons.

It is not applicable to trucks solely guided by mechanical means (rails, guides, etc.) or to remotely controlled trucks, which are not considered to be driverless trucks.

For the purposes of this document, a driverless industrial truck is a powered truck, which is designed to operate automatically. A driverless truck system comprises the control system, which can be part of the truck and/or separate from it, guidance means and power system. Requirements for power sources are not covered in this document.

The condition of the operating zone has a significant effect on the safe operation of the driverless industrial truck. The preparations of the operating zone to eliminate the associated hazards are specified in Annex A.

This document deals with all significant hazards, hazardous situations or hazardous events during all phases of the life of the truck (ISO 12100:2010, 5.4), as listed in Annex B, relevant to the applicable machines when it is used as intended and under conditions of misuse which are reasonably foreseeable by the manufacturer.

It does not give requirements for additional hazards that can occur:

- ▷ during operation in severe conditions (e.g. extreme climates, freezer applications, strong magnetic fields);
- ▷ during operation in nuclear environments;
- ▷ from trucks intended to operate in public zones (in particular ISO 13482);
- ▷ during operation on a public road;
- ▷ during operation in potentially explosive environments;
- ▷ during operation in military applications;
- ▷ during operation with specific hygienic requirements;
- ▷ during operation in ionizing radiation environments;
- ▷ during the transportation of (a) person(s) other than (the) intended rider(s);
- ▷ when handling loads the nature of which can lead to dangerous situations (e.g. molten metals, acids/bases, radiating materials);

▷ for rider positions with elevation function higher than 1 200 mm from the floor/ground to the platform floor.

This document does not contain safety requirements for trailer(s) being towed behind a truck.

This document does not contain safety requirements for elevated operator trucks.

This document is not applicable to trucks manufactured before the date of its publication.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/70660.html>

Published: Q1 2020

Title: Safety of machinery — Emergency stop function — Principles for design

Abstract: ISO 13850:2015 Standard specifies functional requirements and design principles for the emergency stop function on machinery, independent of the type of energy used.

It does not deal with functions such as reversal or limitation of motion, deflection of emissions (e.g. radiation, fluids), shielding, braking or disconnecting, which can be part of the emergency stop function.

The requirements for this International Standard apply to all machines, with exception to:

- machines where an emergency stop would not reduce the risk;
- hand-held or hand-operated machines.

NOTE The requirements for the realization of the emergency stop function based on electrical/electronic technology are described in IEC 60204-1.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/59970.html>

Published: Q4 2015

ISO TC 299

Title: Robotics — Performance criteria and related test methods for service robots — Part 1: Locomotion for wheeled robots

Abstract: ISO 18646-1:2016 describes methods for specifying and evaluating the locomotion performance of wheeled robots in indoor environments.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/63127.html>

Published: Q3 2016

Title: Mobile robots — Vocabulary

Abstract: ISO 19649:2017 defines terms relating to mobile robots that travel on a solid surface and that operate in both industrial robot and service robot applications. It defines terms used for describing mobility, locomotion and other topics relating to the navigation of mobile robots.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/65658.html>

Published: Q2 2017

Title: Robotics — Modularity for service robots — Part 1: General requirements

Abstract: This document presents requirements and guidelines on the specification of modular frameworks, on open modular design and on the integration of modules for realising service robots in various environments, including personal and professional sectors.

The document is targeted at the following user groups:

- ▷ modular service robot framework developers who specify performance frameworks in an unambiguous way;

- ▷ module designers and/or manufacturers who supply end users or robot integrators;
- ▷ service robot integrators who choose applicable modules for building a modular system.

This document includes guidelines on how to apply existing safety and security standards to service robot modules.

This document is not a safety standard.

This document applies specifically to service robots, although the modularity principles presented in this document can be utilized by framework developers, module manufacturers, and module integrators from other fields not necessarily restricted to robotics.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/72715.html>

 Published: Q1 2021

Massrobotics

Title: MassRobotics Interoperability Standard

Abstract: A consortium-built standard to guide robotic automation interoperability and take a step toward this future. The standard will allow robots of different types from various vendors to share status information and operational conventions or “rules of the road” so they can better coexist on a warehouse or factory floor.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.massrobotics.org/2021/05/17/autonomous-mobile-robot-standards-published-by-massrobotics/>

 Published: Q2 2021

VDA

Title: AGV Communication Interface

Abstract: This document describes the communication interface for exchanging order and status data between a central master control and automated guided vehicles (AGV) for intralogistics processes

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.vda.de/vda/en/association/organization/Working-groups/Working-group-on-key-technologies>

 Published: Q1 2022

Title: Functional Safety Of Artificial Intelligence For Machinery Applications (B11 Technical Report)

Abstract: This Technical Report provides guidance for the: implementation of functional safety principles in artificial intelligence (AI) programming when used as a means for machinery safety applications; effective communication between functional safety personnel (who provide the primary technical knowledge of machine(s) system hazards and the application of risk reduction measures) and data scientists / programmers with no or limited machine system knowledge, but who understand the capabilities and limitations of the AI system.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://webstore.ansi.org/Standards/AMT/B11TR102020>

 Published: Q4 2020

Title: Functional Safety for Equipment (Electrical/Fluid Power Control Systems) General Principles for the Design of Safety Control Systems Using ISO 13849-1

Abstract: This American National Standard provides both requirements and guidance for the implementation of safety-related control functions (functional safety) as they relate to electrical, electronic, pneumatic, hydraulic, and mechanical components of control systems.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://i2.saiglobal.com/management/display/index/0/1489677/-/97ca264fe6687eda683b408c56bdadeb>

Published: Q4 2018

Title: Ergonomic Guidelines for the Design, Installation And Use of Machine Tools

Abstract: This document provides ergonomic design guidelines intended to improve quality, performance and safety by reducing fatigue and injury associated with manufacturing systems, including individual and integrated machines and auxiliary components. It is intended to be a resource that can be applied to:

Design or major modification, installation and use of machines and their auxiliary components;

Design of a manufacturing system supporting machines and auxiliary components;

Improve safety, quality and productivity, and reduce errors associated with a manufacturing system.

Integrating ergonomic concepts early in the design process should maximize the impact and cost effectiveness of ergonomic interventions during the design process. The goal of this document is to provide guidance on the practical application of ergonomic principles in order to avoid work-related injuries and musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), increase productivity, and improve product quality.

This document is directed towards technicians, engineers, designers, and safety and health practitioners who deal with general ergonomic issues related to machines. It is not intended to replace in-depth analysis by qualified and experienced ergonomists.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://webstore.ansi.org/Standards/AMT/B11TR12016>

Published: Q4 2016

Title: Guidance to Machinery Manufacturers for Consideration of Related IT-Security (Cyber Security) Aspects

Abstract: This document gives machine manufacturers guidance on potential security aspects in relation to safety of machinery when putting a machine into service or placing it on the market for the first time. It provides essential information to identify and address IT-security threats which can influence the safety of machinery.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://webstore.ansi.org/Standards/AMT/B11TR92019>

Published: Q2 2019

ANSI

Title: Designing for Safety and Lean Manufacturing: A guide on integrating safety and lean manufacturing principles in the use of machinery

Abstract: This document provides guidance on the practical application of safety and lean manufacturing principles to machinery and manufacturing systems for improving performance, safety and quality by reducing injury and waste. The guidelines in this technical report assist machine tool users to minimize waste and risk associated with machinery and manufacturing systems, including individual and integrated machine tools and auxiliary components.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: [preview_B11.TR7-2007.pdf \(ansi.org\)](#)

Published: Q2 2007

Title: Safety Requirements for Large Machines

Abstract: This standard applies to machines with a work envelope equal to or greater than two cubic meters (2 m³) or two meters of linear axis travel, or where personnel are regularly required to enter into the working envelope to perform work or tasks. This standard applies to large machines with a working envelope greater than two cubic meters (meters of travel).

The requirements in this standard apply to all large machines, unless they are specifically covered in or by another standard. This document is intended to be used with both ANSI B11.0 and ANSI B11.19 to execute the risk assessment process and the risk reduction measures, respectively.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://i2.saiglobal.com/management/display/index/0/1120813/-/c86e5bb1249dfcd7eeb7e324b46f2b0>

Published: Q1 2015

ASME

Title: SUBCOMMITTEE ON ROBOTIC ARMS (MANIPULATORS)

Abstract: Develop and maintain Standards for terminology, performance requirements, and related topics for robotic arms (manipulators).

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://cstools.asme.org/csconnect/CommitteePages.cfm?Committee=102674840>

Published: Q2-2022

CEN TC 114 WG 9

Title: SAFETY OF MACHINERY - PREVENTION OF UNEXPECTED START-UP

Abstract: This standard specifies built-in safety measures aimed at preventing unexpected machine start-up (see 3.2) to

allow safe human interventions in danger zones (see Annex A).

This standard applies to unexpected start-up from all types of energy source, i.e.:

- ▷ Power supply, e.g. electrical, hydraulic, pneumatic;
- ▷ Stored energy due to, e.g., gravity, compressed springs;
- ▷ External influences, e.g. from wind;

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: https://shop.standards.ie/en-ie/standards/i-s-en-1037-1995-a1-2008-859147_saig_nsai_nsai_2043874/

Published: Q1 2008

CENELEC

Title: PROTECTION AGAINST ELECTRIC SHOCK - COMMON ASPECTS FOR INSTALLATION AND EQUIPMENT

Abstract: Pertains to the protection of persons and livestock against electric shock.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: https://shop.standards.ie/en-ie/standards/i-s-en-61140-2016-872973_saig_nsai_nsai_2075632/

Published: Q1 2016

CLC SR 70

Title: Degrees of protection provided by enclosures (IP Code) (IEC 60529:1989 (EQV))

Abstract: This standard applies to the classification of degrees of protection provided by enclosures for electrical equipment with a rated voltage not exceeding 72,5 kV.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: https://shop.standards.ie/en-ie/standards/i-s-en-60529-1991-a1-2000-a2-2013-ac-ac-2016-12-ac-2019-872460_saig_nsai_nsai_2799814/

Published: Q1 2020

CLC TC 44X

Title: Safety of machinery - Electrical equipment of machines -- Part 1: General requirements (IEC 60204 -1:2005 (MOD))

Abstract: This part of IEC 60204 applies to the application of electrical, electronic and programmable electronic equipment and systems to machines not portable by hand while working, including a group of machines working together in a co-ordinated manner.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: https://shop.standards.ie/en-ie/standards/i-s-en-60204-1-2018-856074_saig_nsai_nsai_2677824/

Published: Q4 2018

COVR

Title: Test Safety Related Sensor System

Abstract: The purpose of this protocol is to extend the validation of the skill “Maintain Safe Distance” when complex safetyrelated sensor systems (SRSS) are installed within the workcell, by characterizing the SRSS performance. The characterization is based on the measurement of the response time of the system and results accuracy. Results are expressed in human operator position, human operator perimeter violation, human operator movement speed and a true/false detection of the human operator falling to ground.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: <https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/MSD-3.pdf>

Published: Q4 2021

DIN/DKE

Title: German Standardization Roadmap Industrie 4.0, Version 4

Abstract: A Strategic and technically oriented document in which describes the current development status of Industrie 4.0, outlines the requirements for standards, specifications and industry standards, and provides impetus for successful implementation.

Document Type: Landscape

URL: <https://www.din.de/resource/blob/65354/1bed7e8d800cd4712d7d1786584a7a3a/roadmap-i4-0-e-data.pdf>

Published: Q1 2020

VDE/DKE

Title: Development and Trustworthiness of autonomous / cognitive Systems - Part 5: Development at Technology Level

Abstract: VDE-AR-E 2842-61-5

Document Type: Standard_Specification

Published: Q4-2022

Title: Development and Trustworthiness of autonomous / cognitive Systems - Part 2: Management

Abstract: VDE-AR-E 2842-61-2 describes the requirements for the management in order to ensure and support a structured approach to the development of an trustworthy autonomous cognitive system. This entails guidance (e.g. process, procedures synchronized with the overall process), supporting means (e.g. methods, templates) as well as resource planning and activity tracking to ensure the right performance of the system. The obligation is split into three parts: the management on company level, the management during the project and the management after release. VDE-AR-E 2842-61-2 is part of an overall reference lifecycle as a unified approach to achieve and maintain the overall performance of the solution and the intended behavior and trustworthiness of the autonomous / cognitive system. In addition, this could lead to a basis for the qualification and conformity assessment of solutions based on autonomous / cognitive systems including elements of artificial intelligence. This VDE application guide is written in English.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.vde-verlag.de/standards/0800731/vde-ar-e-2842-61-2-anwendungsregel-2021-06.html>

Published: Q2 2021

Title: Development and Trustworthiness of autonomous / cognitive Systems - Part 6: After Release of the Solution

Abstract: VDE-AR-E 2842-61-6 specifies a general framework for the development of trustworthy solutions and trustworthy autonomous / cognitive systems, including the requirements for the subsequent phases of Product life cycle (e. g. production, marketing & sales, operation & maintenance, retirement & repair). It defines a reference lifecycle in analogy to the most important standards for functional safety (i. e. IEC 61508) as a unified approach to achieve and maintain the overall performance of the solution and the intended behavior and trustworthiness of the autonomous / cognitive system. In addition, this could lead to a basis for the qualification and conformity assessment of solutions based on autonomous / cognitive systems including elements of artificial intelligence. The

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.vde-verlag.de/standards/0800732/vde-ar-e-2842-61-6-anwendungsregel-2021-06.html>

Published: Q2 2021

Title: IoT LSP use cases and standards gaps

Abstract: Contains Gap analysis in the context of Smart Manufacturing with respect to Standards Gaps. Proposes some recommendations to overcome potential gaps. Particular attention will be paid on horizontal application layer standardization and to assure an interworking framework among different vertical industrial segments

Document Type: Report

URL: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_tr/103300_103399/103376/01.01.01_60/tr_103376v010101p.pdf

Published: Q4 2016

Title: "Enjoy!" The ETSI Magazine: THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF INDUSTRY

Abstract: On enabling the factory of the future with 5G and time-sensitive networking, and how the area of Robotics benefit from related standards

Document Type: Landscape

URL: https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Magazine/ETSI_Enjoy_MAG_2022_N01_January.pdf

Published: Q1 2022

Title: Digital Enhanced Cordless Telecommunications (DECT); Study on URLLC use cases of vertical industries for DECT evolution and DECT-2020

Abstract: Presents a study of use cases and vertical scenarios for Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC) intended to be used as base requirements for evolving DECT. Applications

/ Use Cases include Home and Building Automation, including Smart Living; Industry automation - Factories of the Future, Industry 4.0; Mobile robots

Document Type: Report

URL: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_tr/103500_103599/103515/01.01.01_60/tr_103515v010101p.pdf

Published: Q1 2018

IEC CISPR/CIS/H

Title: Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) - Part 6-4: Generic standards - Emission standard for industrial environments

Abstract:

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: https://shop.standards.ie/en-ie/standards/en-iec-61000-6-4-2019-1165167_saig_cenelec_cenelec_2771776/

Published: Q3 2019

Title: Environmental testing - Part 2-2: Tests - Test B: Dry heat

Abstract: IEC 60068-2-2:2007 Deals with dry heat tests applicable both to heat-dissipating and non heat-dissipating specimens. For non heat-dissipating specimens, Tests Bb and Bd do not deviate essentially from earlier issues. The object of the dry heat test is limited to the determination of the ability of components, equipment or other articles to be used, transported or stored at high temperature. These dry heat tests do not enable the ability of specimens to withstand or operate during the temperature variations to be assessed. In this case, it would be necessary to use IEC 60068-2-14 Test N: Change of temperature. The dry heat tests are subdivided as follows:

▷ Dry heat test for non heat-dissipating specimens with gradual change of temperature, Bb.

▷ Dry heat tests for heat-dissipating specimens with gradual change of temperature, Bd;

with gradual change of temperature, specimen powered throughout, Be. The procedures given in this standard are normally intended for specimens that achieve temperature stability during the performance of the test procedure. The main changes from the previous edition are as follows: Tests Ba and Bc have been deleted since they were more severe tests than Test Nb, IEC 60068-2-14: Change of temperature. Secondly it was considered justified to delete the 3 % value on the temperature difference between the chamber air and the wall temperatures. Thirdly it is proposed that the test specimen be powered throughout the test where required; and, finally, the annexes have been removed.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://webstore.iec.ch/publication/510>

Published: Q2 2007

Title: Environmental testing - Part 2-1: Tests - Test A: Cold

Abstract: IEC 60068-2-1:2007 Deals with cold tests applicable to both non heat-dissipating and heat-dissipating specimens. For non heat-dissipating specimens, Tests Ab and Ad do not deviate essentially from earlier issues. Test Ae has been added primarily for testing equipment that requires being operational throughout the test, including the conditioning periods. The object of the cold test is limited to the determination of the ability of components, equipment or other articles to be used, transported or stored at low temperature. Cold tests cover by this standard do not enable the ability of specimens to withstand or operate during the temperature variations to be assessed. In this case, it would be necessary to use IEC 60068-2-14. The cold tests are subdivided as follows:

▷ Cold tests for non heat-dissipating specimens: * with gradual change of temperature, Ab;

▷ Cold test for heat-dissipating specimens: * with gradual change of temperature, Ad,

* with gradual change of temperature, specimen powered throughout, Ae.

The procedures given in this standard are normally intended for specimens that achieve temperature stability during the performance of the test procedure. Temperature chamber(s) are constructed and

verified in accordance with specifications IEC 60068-3-5 and IEC 60068-3-7. Further guidance for dry heat and cold tests can be found in IEC 60068-3-1 and general guidance in IEC 60068-1. This sixth edition deals with cold tests applicable both to non heat-dissipating and heat-dissipating specimens. For non heat-dissipating specimens, Tests Ab and Ad do not deviate essentially from earlier issues. Test Ae has been added primary for testing equipment that requires being operational throughout the test including the conditioning periods.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://webstore.iec.ch/publication/502>

 Published: Q1 2007

IEC TC 23 SC 23G

Title: Appliance couplers for household and similar general purposes - Part 1: General requirements

Abstract: This part of IEC 60320 sets the general requirements for appliance couplers for two poles and two poles with earth contact and for the connection of electrical devices for household and similar onto the mains supply.

This document is also valid for appliance inlets/appliance outlets integrated or incorporated in appliances.

The rated voltage does not exceed 250 V (AC) and the rated current does not exceed 16 A.

Appliance couplers complying with this document are suitable for normal use at ambient temperatures not normally exceeding +40 °C, but their average over a period of 24 h does not exceed +35 °C, with a lower limit of the ambient air temperature of -5 °C.

Annex E provides test requirements for derating the operating current of an accessory when used in ambient temperatures above +35 °C up to and including +90 °C.

Appliance couplers are not suitable for:

- ▷ use in place of plug and socket-outlet systems according to IEC 60884-1;
- ▷ use in place of devices for connecting luminaires (DCLs) according to IEC 61995 or luminaire supporting couplers (LSCs);
- ▷ use in place of installation couplers according to IEC 61535.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: IEC 60320-1:2021 CMV | IEC Webstore

 Published: Q3 2021

IEC TC 65

Title: Security for industrial automation and control systems - Part 3-2: Security risk assessment for system design

Abstract: IEC 62443-3-2:2020 establishes requirements for:

- ▷ defining a system under consideration (SUC) for an industrial automation and control system (IACS);
- ▷ partitioning the SUC into zones and conduits;
- ▷ assessing risk for each zone and conduit;
- ▷ establishing the target security level (SL-T) for each zone and conduit; and
- ▷ documenting the security requirements.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://webstore.iec.ch/publication/30727>

 Published: Q2 2020

IEC TC 65 SC 65A

Title: Electrical equipment for measurement, control and laboratory use - EMC requirements – Part 3-1: Immunity requirements for safety-related systems and for equipment intended to perform safety-related functions (functional safety) – General industrial applic

Abstract:

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://webstore.iec.ch/publication/30986>

Published: Q2 2017

IEC TC 65 SC 65E

Title: Engineering data exchange format for use in industrial automation systems engineering - Automation Markup Language - Part 1: Architecture and general requirements

Abstract: IEC 62714-1:2018 is a solution for data exchange focusing on the domain of automation engineering. The data exchange format defined in the IEC 62714 series (Automation Markup Language, AML) is an XML schema based data format and has been developed in order to support the data exchange in a heterogeneous engineering tools landscape. The goal of AML is to interconnect engineering tools in their different disciplines, e.g. mechanical plant engineering, electrical design, process engineering, process control engineering, HMI development, PLC programming, robot programming, etc. This second edition cancels and replaces the first edition published in 2014. This edition constitutes a technical revision. This edition includes the following significant technical changes with respect to the previous edition:

- a) use of CAEX 3.0 according to IEC 62424:2016
- b) improved modelling of references to documents outside of the scope of the present standard,
- c) modelling of references between CAEX attributes and items in external documents,
- d) revised role libraries,
- e) modified Port concept,
- f) modelling of multilingual expressions,
- g) modelling of structured attribute lists or array,
- h) a new AML container format,
- i) a new standard AML attribute library

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://webstore.iec.ch/publication/32339>

Published: Q2 2018

Title: Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) - Part 6-2: Generic standards - Immunity standard for industrial environments (IEC 61000-6-2:2016)

Abstract: This part of IEC 61000 for EMC immunity requirements applies to electrical and electronic equipment intended for use in industrial locations, as described below.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: https://shop.standards.ie/en-ie/standards/i-s-en-iec-61000-6-2-2019-1144368_saig_nsai_nsai_2711912/

Published: Q1 2019

Title: Standard for Semantic Maps for Autonomous Robots - Part 1: Use Cases and Requirements

Abstract: This standard defines requirements of semantic maps for autonomous robots from application scenarios and use cases.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3140.1/11546/>

 Published: Q4-2028

Title: Standard for Semantic Maps for Autonomous Robots - Part 2: Framework and Application Development Interface

Abstract: This standard defines a basic data model, data exchange format, and application framework of semantic maps for autonomous robots based on the requirements from use cases in IEEE Standard P3140.1.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3140.2/11547/>

 Published: Q4-2028

Title: Recommended Practice for Human-Robot Interaction Design of Human Subject Studies

Abstract: This recommended practice outlines best practices and requirements for the development of designs of human-subject experiments in human-robot interaction research.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

 URL: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3108/10710/>

 Published: Q4 2025

Title: 3D Map Data Representation for Robotics and Automation

Abstract: This standard extends the IEEE 1873-2015™ Standard for Robot Map Data Representation from two-dimensional (2D) maps to three-dimensional (3D) maps.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/2751/6994/>

 Published: Q4 2024

Title: Standard for Ethically Driven Nudging for Robotic, Intelligent and Autonomous Systems

Abstract: “Nudges” as exhibited by robotic, intelligent or autonomous systems are defined as overt or hidden suggestions or manipulations designed to influence the behavior or emotions of a user. This standard establishes a delineation of typical nudges (currently in use or that could be created). It contains concepts, functions and benefits necessary to establish and ensure ethically driven methodologies for the design of the robotic, intelligent and autonomous systems that incorporate them.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/7008/7095/>

 Published: Q4 2025

Title: IEEE Ontological Standard for Ethically Driven Robotics and Automation Systems

Abstract: A set of ontologies with different abstraction levels that contain concepts, definitions, axioms, and use cases that assist in the development of ethically driven methodologies for the design of robots and automation systems is established by this standard.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/7007/7070/>

 Published: Q4 2021

Title: IEEE Standard for Autonomous Robotics (AuR) Ontology

Abstract: This standard extends IEEE Std 1872-2015, IEEE Standard for Ontologies for Robotics and Automation, to represent additional domain-specific concepts, definitions, and axioms commonly used in Autonomous Robotics (AuR). This standard is general and can be used in many ways--for example, to specify the domain knowledge needed to unambiguously describe the design patterns of AuR systems; to represent AuR system architectures in a unified way; or as a guideline to build autonomous systems consisting of robots operating in various environments.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1872.2/7094/>

 Published: Q2 2022

Title: Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots

Abstract: This standard defines additional requirements for the Autonomous Robot (AuR) ontology to address reasoning on multiple robots, extending the baseline ontology defined in IEEE 1872.2-2021. Ontological concepts and domain-specific axioms are defined for (a) representation, reasoning, and behaviors for autonomy, (b) multiple autonomous robots and cloud robotics, (c) artificial intelligence and machine learning for autonomous robots, (d) affordances in human robot interaction, and (e) trust and security for autonomous robotics. Use cases and case studies for the design of AuR are also described.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1872.3/11037/>

 Published: Q2 2026

ISO TC 299

Title: Robots and robotic devices — Collaborative robots

Abstract: ISO/TS 15066:2016 specifies safety requirements for collaborative industrial robot systems and the work environment, and supplements the requirements and guidance on collaborative industrial robot operation given in ISO 10218-1 and ISO 10218-2.

ISO/TS 15066:2016 applies to industrial robot systems as described in ISO 10218-1 and ISO 10218-2. It does not apply to non-industrial robots, although the safety principles presented can be useful to other areas of robotics.

NOTE This Technical Specification does not apply to collaborative applications designed prior to its publication

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/62996.html>

 Published: Q1 2016

ISO TC 159 SC 1

Title: Ergonomics principles in the design of work systems

Abstract: ISO 6385:2016 establishes the fundamental principles of ergonomics as basic guidelines for the design of work systems and defines relevant basic terms. It describes an integrated approach to the design of work systems, where ergonomists will cooperate with others involved in the design, with attention to the human, the social and the technical requirements in a balanced manner during the design process.

Users of this International Standard will include executives, managers, workers (and their

representatives, when appropriate) and professionals, such as ergonomists, project managers and designers who are involved in the design or redesign of work systems. Those who use this International Standard can find a general knowledge of ergonomics (human factors), engineering, design, quality and project management helpful.

The term “work system” in this International Standard is used to indicate a large variety of working situations, including permanent and flexible work places. The intention of this International Standard is to assist in the improvement, (re)design or change of work systems. Work systems involve combinations of workers and equipment, within a given space and environment, and the interactions between these components within a work organization. Work systems vary in complexity and characteristics, for example, the use of temporary work systems. Some examples of work systems in different areas are the following:

- ▷ production, e.g. machine operator and machine, worker and assembly line;
- ▷ transportation, e.g. driver and car or lorry, personnel in an airport;
- ▷ support, e.g. maintenance technician with work equipment;
- ▷ commercial, e.g. office worker with workstation, mobile worker with a tablet computer, cook in a restaurant kitchen;
- ▷ other areas like health care, teaching and training.

The observance of ergonomic principles applies to all phases throughout the life cycle of the work system from conception through development, realization and implementation, utilization, maintenance and support to decommissioning.

The systems approach in this International Standard gives guidance to the users of this International Standard in existing and new situations.

The definitions and ergonomic principles specified in this International Standard apply to the design of optimal working conditions with regard to human well-being, safety and health, including the development of existing skills and the acquisition of new ones, while taking into account technological and economic effectiveness and efficiency.

The principles in this International Standard are applicable to many other human activities, e.g. in the design of products for domestic and leisure activities. A more general description of the principles in this International Standard can be found in ISO 26800.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/63785.html>

 Published: Q3 2016

ISO TC 159 SC 5

Title: Ergonomics of the thermal environment — Methods for the assessment of human responses to contact with surfaces — Part 1: Hot surfaces

Abstract: ISO 15536-1:2006 provides temperature threshold values for burns that occur when human skin is in contact with a hot solid surface. It also describes methods for the assessment of the risks of burning, when humans could or might touch hot surfaces with their unprotected skin.

In addition, ISO 13732-1:2006 gives guidance for cases where it is necessary to specify temperature limit values for hot surfaces, but does not set surface temperature limit values.

ISO 13732-1:2006 deals with contact periods of 0,5 s and longer.

It is applicable to contact when the surface temperature is essentially maintained during the contact.

It is not applicable if a large area of the skin (approximately 10 % or more of the skin of the whole body) can be in contact with the hot surface. Neither does it apply to skin contact of more than 10 % of the head or contact which could result in burns of vital areas of the face.

ISO 13732-1:2006 is applicable to the hot surfaces of all kind of objects: equipment, products, buildings, natural objects, etc. It is applicable to hot surfaces of products that may be touched by healthy adults, children, elderly people and also by people with physical disabilities. For the purposes of simplification, it mentions only products; nevertheless, it applies to all other objects as well. It is applicable to products used in any environment, e.g. in the workplace, in the home.

It does not provide data for the protection against discomfort or pain.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/43558.html>

Published: Q3 2006

ISO TC 199

Title: Safety of machinery — Prevention of unexpected start-up

Abstract: ISO 14118:2017 specifies requirements for designed-in means aimed at preventing unexpected machine start-up (see 3.2) to allow safe human interventions in danger zones (see Annex A).

ISO 14118:2017 applies to unexpected start-up from all types of energy source, i.e.:

- power supply, e.g. electrical, hydraulic, pneumatic;
- stored energy due to, e.g. gravity, compressed springs;
- external influences, e.g. from wind.

ISO 14118:2017 does not specify performance levels or safety integrity levels for safety-related parts of control systems. While available means to prevent unexpected start-up are identified, this document does not specify the means for the prevention of unexpected machine start-up for specific machines.

NOTE A type-C standard can define the required means for the prevention of harm arising from unexpected start-up. Otherwise, the requirements for a specific machine need to be determined by risk assessment outside the scope of this document.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/66460.html>

Published: Q4 2017

Title: Manipulating industrial robots – Mechanical interfaces

Abstract: ISO 9409-1:2004 defines the main dimensions, designation and marking for a circular plate as mechanical interface. It is intended to ensure the exchangeability and to keep the orientation of hand-mounted end effectors.

It does not define other requirements of the end effector coupling device.

It does not contain any correlation of load-carrying ranges, as it is expected that the appropriate interface is selected depending on the application and the load-carrying capacity of the robot.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: [ISO 9409-1:2004 Manipulating industrial robots Mechanical interf \(standards.ie\)](https://www.iso.org/standard/9409-1-2004.html)

Published: Q1 2004

ITU-T

Title: Requirements and functional model for a ubiquitous network robot platform that supports ubiquitous sensor network applications and services

Abstract: Defines a ubiquitous network robot platform, and to identify its requirements and functional model. The use of standard interfaces for the ubiquitous network robot platform will ensure network robot service reusability, portability across several network robot services, and network accessibility and interoperability by the ubiquitous sensor network (USN).

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-F.747.3-201303-I/en>

Published: Q1 2013

NGMN

Title: 6G Use Cases and Analysis by NGMN V1.0

Abstract: Robot Network Fabric and Cobots in the Collection and assessment of proposed use cases for 6G, explore their implications for 6G R&D activities, and enlighten the way forward. It is the second deliverable in the NGMN Alliance 6G Project and follows from its publication of '6G Drivers and Vision' in April 2021.

Document Type: Report

URL: <https://www.ngmn.org/wp-content/uploads/NGMN-6G-Use-Cases-and-Analysis.pdf>

Published: Q1 2022

Title: Manufacturing /Robotics in manufacturing; COLLABORATIVE ROBOTS

Abstract: Provides an Overview on Projects and Programs on COLLABORATIVE ROBOTS

Document Type: Report

URL: <https://www.nist.gov/collaborative-robots>

Published: Q1 2022

RIA

Title: Testing methods for Speed and Separation Monitoring (SSM) collaborative robot systems

Abstract: The scope of this Technical Report is to provide test methods and metrics for validating separation distances of robot applications using Speed and Separation Monitoring (SSM) in accordance with ANSI/RIA R15.06 and RIA TR R15.606. This Technical Report also provides guidance on determining how speeds and positions of robot systems, workpieces, and obstacles should be measured, and under what conditions such measurements should be made.

This document is informative in nature and is not a standard. The use of the word "shall" and "should" in a particular statement indicates the relative importance of specific criteria or features indicated in ANSI/RIA R15.06, RIA TR R15.606, and RIA R15.08.

Document Type: Report

URL: <https://www.ieee-ras.org/industry-government/standards/standards-strategy-meeting>

Published: Q4-2022

BBF

Title: TR-436 Access & Home Network O&M Automation/Intelligence

Abstract: As part of Autonomic/Autonomous Networks (ANs) paradigm, the document presents a Framework for intelligent and automated O&M for Access & Home networks, which includes: 1) Automatically identify typical anomalies and faults in Access & Home network based on Machine Learning (ML), Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms and expert experience, realize rapid troubleshooting, and thus reduce invalid on-site and sporadic issues. 2) Perform predictive analysis based on ML and AI to achieve preventive O&M and self-healing in case of failure.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.broadband-forum.org/technical/download/TR-436.pdf>

Published: Q1 2021

Title: Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) Release 4; Management and Orchestration; Report on enabling autonomous management in NFV-MANO

Abstract:

Document Type: Report

URL: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gr/NFV-IFA/001_099/041/04.01.01_60/gr_NFV-IFA041v040101p.pdf

Published: Q3-2020

Title: Autonomic network engineering for the self-managing Future Internet (AFI); Generic Autonomic Network Architecture; Part 2: An Architectural Reference Model for Autonomic Networking, Cognitive Networking and Self-Management

Abstract:

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/103100_103199/10319502/01.01.01_60/ts_10319502v010101p.pdf

Published: Q2 2018

IEEE

Title: IEEE INGR (International Network Generations Roadmap)/Future Networks, Standardization Building Blocks (SBB) Roadmap Chapter

Abstract: Discusses Standards Roadmaps for Future Networks, including 5G/6G, as well as in the area of Autonomic/Autonomous Networking (ANs) Standards. The Emerging Industry Requirement for Standardization of a Blueprint for Common Operational Principles for Autonomic/Autonomous Networks (COPAAN) is presented in relation to the Autonomic/Autonomous Networking (ANs) paradigm. The connection of COPAAN and Robotics is illustrated.

Document Type: Whitepaper_or_Report

URL: <https://futurenetworks.ieee.org/roadmap>

Published: Q1 2022

ITU-T

Title: ITU-T Focus Group on “Autonomous Networks” (FG-AN)

Abstract: Provides information on Study to identify and close gaps in Standards for Autonomous Networks (ANs) to complement Standards on ANs developed elsewhere such as the ETSI GANA related Standards

Document Type: Landscape

URL: https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/an/Documents/FG-AN_Terms_of_Reference.pdf?csf=1&e=dRZrwa

Published: Q4 2020

NGMN

Title: 5G End-to-End Architecture Framework by NGMN Alliance, v3.0.8

Abstract: Outlines Requirements for Autonomic Networking and Autonomic Management & Control in 5G Networks

Document Type: Whitepaper_or_Report

URL: https://www.ngmn.org/wp-content/uploads/Publications/2019/190916-NGMN_E2EArchFramework_v3.0.8.pdf

Published: Q4 2019

Title: ODA Functional Architecture Guidebook

Abstract:

Document Type: Report

URL: <https://www.tmforum.org/resources/standard/gb1022-oda-functional-architecture-guidebook-v1-1-0/>

Published: Q1-2021

ANSI/RIA

Title: Industrial Mobile Robots - Safety Requirements - Part 1: Requirements For The Industrial Mobile Robot

Abstract: Specifies safety requirements for industrial mobile robots (IMRs). It describes basic hazards associated with IMRs in an industrial environment (See Clause 3.12), and provides requirements to eliminate or adequately reduce, the risks associated with these hazards.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: Industrial Mobile Robots - Safety Requirements - Part 1: Requirements For The Industrial Mobile Robot

Published: 2020

CEN

Title: Guidelines for the development and use of safety testing procedures in human-robot collaboration

Abstract: This document gives guidelines for a uniform framework, transversal with respect to the different robot categories and limited to those robots and robotic applications characterized by human-robot collaboration, for the development and/or use of testing procedures, applicable to different robot categories and use scenarios. This document is informative and is not aimed at substituting or simplifying verification and/or validation procedures required by standards. The objectives of

this document are the following: — define an approach for the development and use of procedures for testing safety in human-robot collaboration at a system level, based on safety-relevant human-robot collaboration skills and limited to the mechanical hazards; — define a comprehensive list of application-driven, technology-invariant safety-relevant human-robot collaboration skills valid across different domains; — provide a template for system-level validation protocols; — by way of example, present two system-level validation protocols, applicable to multiple domains. This document does not apply to the following devices, systems and applications: autonomous vehicles for the transportation of persons, drones, rescue robots (including ground, marine and aerial vehicles), surgical robots in relation to the body of the patient, passive wearable devices, external limb prostheses. NOTE 1 This document aims at providing harmonization in the compilation of structured testing procedures, to supplement safety validation of specific robot applications, building, where possible, on test methods provided in the relevant standards. It does not propose any safety requirement, nor is it intended to provide alternatives for or simplification of the relevant standards for each robot category. Users of this document are expected to be proficient in directives, regulations and standards applicable for the specific robot system and application. An overview of robot categorization is provided in A.1. NOTE 2 This document does not address “functional safety” (e.g. the performance level of safety-related parts of control systems), nor criteria for its validation and verification.

Document Type: Report

URL: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/news-and-events/news/2021/workshop/2021-07-30-draft-cwa-safety-in-close-human-robot-interaction/>

Published: Q1 2022

Title: Test Robot Arm for Collision with Fixed Object (measurement of pressure over time)

Abstract: The specific purpose of this protocol is to validate the safety skill “limit interaction energy” by measurement. Its scope is limited to robot arms operating in the domain Manufacturing. In this context, the skill “limit interaction energy” is often used to protect workers from injuries caused by robot collisions where the robot traps a part of the human body against a fixed obstacle. The validation of this protocol requires that the reader has a bio-fidel force and pressure measurement device available. The instrument must allow for measuring the pressure history during the collision.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: [https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/ROB-LIE-2%20Test%20Robot%20Arm%20for%20Collision%20with%20Fixed%20Object%20\(pressure%20over%20time\).pdf](https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/ROB-LIE-2%20Test%20Robot%20Arm%20for%20Collision%20with%20Fixed%20Object%20(pressure%20over%20time).pdf)

Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test Prevention of Spatial Overreaching for the Subject (Robot in Control)

Abstract: The purpose of this protocol is to validate the safety skill “limit range of movement” for rehabilitation robots, where a limb of a subject has a connection point with the robot (either free or restrained) and the robot can move that point within a 3D volume. The range of motion is assessed using opto-electronic 3D marker tracking.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: <https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/ROB-LRM-2%20Test%20Prevention%20Spatial%20Overreaching%20for%20the%20Subject-Robot%20in%20Control.pdf>

Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test Gripper for Limiting Physical Interaction Energy

Abstract: The specific purpose of this protocol is to validate the safety skill “limit interaction energy” by measurement for robotic grippers. In this context, the skill “limit interaction energy” is commonly used to protect workers from injuries caused by clamping and squeezing of body parts by the closing gripper. The validation of this protocol requires that the reader has a bio-fidelic measurement instrument available to measure contact forces and pressures.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/GRI-LIE-1%20Test%20Gripper%20for%20Limiting%20Physical%20Interaction%20Energy_2021-09-08.pdf

 Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test prevention of spatial overreaching for the subject Human in (shared) control testing with optical measurement system

Abstract: The purpose of this protocol is to validate the safety skill “limit range of movement” for rehabilitation robots, where a limb of a subject has a connection point with the robot (either free or restrained) and the robot can move that point within a 3D volume.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

 URL: [https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/ROB-LRM-3%20Test%20prevention%20spatial%20overreaching%20for%20the%20subject%20%E2%80%93%20Human%20in%20\(co-\)control%20-%20optical%20measurement%20system.pdf](https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/ROB-LRM-3%20Test%20prevention%20spatial%20overreaching%20for%20the%20subject%20%E2%80%93%20Human%20in%20(co-)control%20-%20optical%20measurement%20system.pdf)

 Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test Robot Arm for Collision with a Movable Object (measurement of peak pressure)

Abstract: The specific purpose of this protocol is to validate the safety skill “limit interaction energy” by measurement. Its scope is limited to robot arms operating in the domain Manufacturing. In this context, the skill “limit interaction energy” is often used to protect workers from injuries caused by robot collisions where the robot hits a part of the human body that can freely move. The validation of this protocol requires that the reader has a bio-fidel force and pressure measurement device available. The instrument must allow for measuring the highest pressure during the collision.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

 URL: [https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/ROB-LIE-3%20Test%20Robot%20Arm%20for%20Collision%20with%20a%20Movable%20Object%20\(peak%20pressure\).pdf](https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/ROB-LIE-3%20Test%20Robot%20Arm%20for%20Collision%20with%20a%20Movable%20Object%20(peak%20pressure).pdf)

 Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test Limit Restraining Energy for lower limb Exoskeletons

Abstract: This protocol is to be used to test the restraining energy that can be applied to a human subject during use of an exoskeleton used for gait support using an instrumented limb used in the medical domain as well as at . This protocol is both aimed at exoskeletons used in the industrial, logistics or agricultural domain Readiness Level Description .

Document Type: Recommended Practice

 URL: <https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/EXO-LRE-1%20Test%20Limit%20Restraining%20Energy%20for%20lower%20limb%20Exoskeleton.pdf>

 Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test 3D Safety Sensors in Speed and Separation Monitoring Cobot Applications

Abstract: The purpose of this protocol is to validate suitability of 3D sensors, particularly LiDAR scanners, for improving the skill “Maintain Safe Distance” in advanced Speed and Separation Monitoring (SSM) cobot applications . Besides the sensors’ technical characteristics, the data processing, and decision-making abilities of an associated intelligent control system (ICS) are the subject of validation. Such ICS periodically acquires of a COBOT and an operator, eventually predicts their positions in the positions near future, and adjusts the COBOT’s velocity to keep their mutual distance above the accordingly updated protective separation distance (PSD). The validation test checks with assistance of a high-speed high-resolution camera whether the ICS implements the SSM functionality successfully to prevent collisions between the robot and the operator in a systematically chosen repertoire of collaborative situations identified as potentially hazardous in the risk assessment. This protocol was developed in the COVR funded FSTP project “CobotSense” by FOKUS TECH, the Maribor, and FANUC ADRIA, and was published as a deliverable for that project.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

 URL: https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/ROB-MSD-3-Test_3D_Safety_Sensors_in_Speed_and_Separation_Monitoring_Cobot_Applications.pdf

 Published: Q4 2021

Title: Collaborative robot systems - Design of systems with “Power and Force Limiting” function

Abstract: Collaborating robot systems can be used in the function “Power and Force Limiting” without the need for traditional limiting” function without the need for traditional such as fences and light curtains. come into play. Regarding the requirements of standards, regulations and ordinances, as well as the use of research results, there is a need for practical practical guidance for manufacturers, system integrators, operators, accident insurance institutions and certification bodies.

Document Type: Report

URL: https://www.dguv.de/medien/fb-holzundmetall/publikationen-dokumente/infoblaetter/infobl_englisch/080_collaborativerobotsystems.pdf

Published: Q3 2008

Title: BG/BGIA risk assessment recommendations according to machinery directive

Abstract: The BG/BGIA recommendations for the risk assessment according to the machinery directive are published by the – German Institutions for Statutory Accident Insurance and – the Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (BGIA). Their objective is to provide companies an aid for the accident prevention related part of risk assessment. These BG/BGIA recommendations were drawn up in collaboration with the – Expert Committee for Machine Construction, Production Systems and Steel Construction of the Institution for Statutory Accident Insurance and Prevention Metall Nord Süd (Fachausschuss Maschinenbau, Fertigungssysteme, Stahlbau der Berufsgenossenschaft Metall Nord Süd).

Document Type: Report

URL: <https://publikationen.dguv.de/forschung/ifa/allgemeine-informationen/4387/bg/bgia-risk-assesment-recommendations-according-to-machinery-directive-design-of-workplaces-with>

Published: Q1 2011

Title: Short Range Devices (SRD); Harmonised Standard for access to radio spectrum; Inductive loop systems for robotic mowers operating within the frequency range 100 Hz to 148,5 kHz

Abstract:

Document Type: Report

URL: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_en/303400_303499/303447/01.03.01_30/en_303447v010301v.pdf

Published: Ongoing

GSMA

Title: Enabling 5G Autonomous Robots in the Factory

Abstract: Webinar Addresses: Connected, smarter robots are considered crucial to delivering efficiencies through automation and remote monitoring, in areas such as factory floors. 5G IoT will make it possible for robots to connect with other robots, devices and systems in a way that wasn't possible before. The webinar takes a deep dive into 5G Autonomous Mobile Robots, the functionality and solutions they can bring to an industrial setting, and the role of 5G IoT technologies in enabling them.

Webinar addresses: Enabling the fourth industrial revolution; where interconnectivity and interoperability can deliver large scale automation and process orchestration for manufacturing and the wider industrial sectors. Connected, smarter robots are considered crucial to delivering efficiencies through automation and remote monitoring, in areas such as factory floors. 5G IoT will make it possible for robots to connect with other robots, devices and systems in a way that wasn't possible before. The webinar takes a deep dive into 5G Autonomous Mobile Robots, the functionality and solutions they can bring to an industrial setting, and the role of 5G IoT technologies in enabling them.

Document Type: Landscape

URL: https://www.gsma.com/iot/gsma_events/webtalk-5g-autonomous-robots/

Published: Q4 2021

Title: 5G Brings Autonomous Robots To Life

Abstract: Discuss How 5G network enables robots to transport goods across manufacturing plants

Document Type: Whitepaper_or_Report

URL: <https://www.gsma.com/iot/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/2022-03-GSMA-APAC-5G-Case-Study-AIS-5G-Smart-Factory.pdf>

Published: Q1 2022

ISO TC 110

Title: Industrial trucks — Safety requirements and verification — Part 4: Driverless industrial trucks and their systems

Abstract: This document specifies safety requirements and the means for their verification for driverless industrial trucks (hereafter referred to as trucks) and their systems.

Examples of driverless industrial trucks (trucks of ISO 5053-1) can also be known as: “automated guided vehicle”, “autonomous mobile robot”, “bots”, “automated guided cart”, “tunnel tugger”, “under cart”, etc.

This document also contains requirements for driverless industrial trucks which are provided with:

- ▷ — automatic modes which either require operators’ action(s) to initiate or enable such automatic operations;
- ▷ the capability to transport one or more riders (which are neither considered as drivers nor as operators);
- ▷ additional manual modes which allow operators to operate the truck manually; or
- ▷ a maintenance mode which allows manual operation of truck functions for maintenance reasons.

It is not applicable to trucks solely guided by mechanical means (rails, guides, etc.) or to remotely controlled trucks, which are not considered to be driverless trucks.

For the purposes of this document, a driverless industrial truck is a powered truck, which is designed to operate automatically. A driverless truck system comprises the control system, which can be part of the truck and/or separate from it, guidance means and power system. Requirements for power sources are not covered in this document.

The condition of the operating zone has a significant effect on the safe operation of the driverless industrial truck. The preparations of the operating zone to eliminate the associated hazards are specified in Annex A.

This document deals with all significant hazards, hazardous situations or hazardous events during all phases of the life of the truck (ISO 12100:2010, 5.4), as listed in Annex B, relevant to the applicable machines when it is used as intended and under conditions of misuse which are reasonably foreseeable by the manufacturer.

It does not give requirements for additional hazards that can occur:

- ▷ during operation in severe conditions (e.g. extreme climates, freezer applications, strong magnetic fields);
- ▷ during operation in nuclear environments;
- ▷ from trucks intended to operate in public zones (in particular ISO 13482);
- ▷ during operation on a public road;
- ▷ during operation in potentially explosive environments;
- ▷ during operation in military applications;
- ▷ during operation with specific hygienic requirements;
- ▷ during operation in ionizing radiation environments;
- ▷ during the transportation of (a) person(s) other than (the) intended rider(s);
- ▷ when handling loads the nature of which can lead to dangerous situations (e.g. molten metals, acids/bases, radiating materials);
- ▷ for rider positions with elevation function higher than 1 200 mm from the floor/ground to the platform floor.

This document does not contain safety requirements for trailer(s) being towed behind a truck.

This document does not contain safety requirements for elevated operator trucks.

This document is not applicable to trucks manufactured before the date of its publication.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/70660.html>

 Published: Q1 2020

ISO TC 184 SC 5

Title: Advanced automation technologies and their applications — Requirements for establishing manufacturing enterprise process interoperability — Part 1: Framework for enterprise interoperability

Abstract: The purpose of ISO 11354-1:2011 is to specify a Framework for Enterprise Interoperability (FEI) that establishes dimensions and viewpoints to address interoperability barriers, their potential solutions, and the relationships between them.

ISO 11354 applies to manufacturing enterprises, but can also apply to other kinds of enterprises. It is intended for use by stakeholders who are concerned with developing and deploying solutions based on information and communication technology for manufacturing enterprise process interoperability. It focuses on, but is not restricted to, enterprise (manufacturing or service) interoperability.

ISO 11354-1:2011 specifies the following:

viewpoints for addressing stakeholder concerns for the exchange of entities (information objects or physical objects) at the operational levels of enterprises at which interoperability is required;

a framework for structuring these stakeholder concerns (business, process, service, data), the barriers relating to enterprise interoperability (conceptual, technological, organizational) and the approaches to overcome barriers (integrated, unified, federated), with contents identifying the various kinds of solutions available to enable interoperability.

ISO 11354-1:2011 does not specify the specific mechanisms for the exchange of entities (information objects or physical objects), nor the manner in which interoperability solutions are implemented.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/50417.html>

 Published: Q3 2011

Title: Enterprise integration — Framework for enterprise modelling

Abstract: ISO 19439:2006 specifies a framework conforming to requirements of ISO 15704, which serves as a common basis to identify and coordinate standards development for modelling of enterprises, emphasising, but not restricted to, computer integrated manufacturing. ISO 19439:2006 also serves as the basis for further standards for the development of models that will be computer-enactable and enable business process model-based decision support leading to model-based operation, monitoring and control.

In ISO 19439:2006, four enterprise model views are defined in this framework. Additional views for particular user concerns can be generated but these additional views are not part of this International Standard. Possible additional views are identified in ISO 15704.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/33833.html>

 Published: Q2 2006

ISO TC 299

Title: Robotics — Safety design for industrial robot systems — Part 2: Manual load/unload stations

Abstract: ISO/TR 20218-2:2017 is applicable to robot systems for manual load/unload applications in which a hazard zone is safeguarded by preventing access to it. For this type of application, it is important to consider the need for both access restrictions to hazard zones and for ergonomically suitable work places.

ISO/TR 20218-2:2017 supplements ISO 10218-2:2011 and provides additional information and guidance on reducing the risk of intrusion into the hazard zones in the design and safeguarding of manual load/unload installations.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/70584.html>

 Published: Q4 2017

Title: Manipulating industrial robots — Object handling with grasp-type grippers — Vocabulary and presentation of characteristics

Abstract: ISO 14539 is one of a series of standards dealing with the requirements of manipulating industrial robots. Other documents cover such topics as terminology, general characteristics, coordinate systems, performance criteria and related test methods, safety, mechanical interfaces and graphical user interfaces for programming

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: ISO - ISO 14539:2000 - Manipulating industrial robots — Object handling with grasp-type grippers — Vocabulary and presentation of characteristics

 Published: Q4 2000

Title: Robots and robotic devices — Safety requirements for industrial robots — Part 2: Robot systems and integration

Abstract: ISO 10218-2:2011 specifies safety requirements for the integration of industrial robots and industrial robot systems as defined in ISO 10218-1, and industrial robot cell(s). The integration includes the following:

- ▷ the design, manufacturing, installation, operation, maintenance and decommissioning of the industrial robot system or cell;
- ▷ necessary information for the design, manufacturing, installation, operation, maintenance and decommissioning of the industrial robot system or cell;
- ▷ component devices of the industrial robot system or cell.

ISO 10218-2:2011 describes the basic hazards and hazardous situations identified with these systems, and provides requirements to eliminate or adequately reduce the risks associated with these hazards. ISO 10218-2:2011 also specifies requirements for the industrial robot system as part of an integrated manufacturing system. ISO 10218-2:2011 does not deal specifically with hazards associated with processes (e.g. laser radiation, ejected chips, welding smoke). Other standards can be applicable to these process hazards.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

 URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/41571.html>

 Published: Q3 2011

Title: Manipulating industrial robots — Presentation of characteristics

Abstract: This International Standard specifies how characteristics of robots shall be presented by the manufacturer.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/28794.html>

Published: Q2 1999

Title: Manipulating industrial robots — Informative guide on test equipment and metrology methods of operation for robot performance evaluation in accordance with ISO 9283

Abstract: Supplies information on the state-of-the-art of test equipment operating principles. Additional information is provided that describes the applications of current test equipment technology to ISO 9283.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: [ISO - ISO/TR 13309:1995 - Manipulating industrial robots — Informative guide on test equipment and metrology methods of operation for robot performance evaluation in accordance with ISO 9283](#)

Published: Q2 1995

Title: Robots for industrial environments — Automatic end effector exchange systems — Vocabulary

Abstract: This document defines terms relevant to automatic end-effector exchange systems used as a part of robot systems in accordance with ISO 10218-2.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: [ISO - ISO 11593:2022 - Robots for industrial environments — Automatic end effector exchange systems — Vocabulary](#)

Published: Q1 2022

Title: Robots and robotic devices — Safety requirements for personal care robots

Abstract: Robots and robotic devices — Safety requirements for personal care robots

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: [ISO - ISO 13482:2014 - Robots and robotic devices — Safety requirements for personal care robots](#)

Published: Q1 2014

Title: Robots and robotic devices - Safety requirements for industrial robots - Part 2: Robot systems and integration

Abstract: Harmonised to the EU Machinery Directive, this adopted ISO Standard addresses the safety requirements addressing particular hazards that are presented by industrial robot systems when integrated and installed in industrial robot cells and lines. As a harmonised standard it can be used to demonstrate compliance required for CE marking of the system.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/41571.html?browse=tc>

Published: 2011

Title: Robotics — Collaborative applications — Test methods for measuring forces and pressures in quasi-static and transient contacts between robots and human

Abstract:

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/82488.html>

Published:

Title: Industrial Robots And Robot Systems - Safety Requirements - Collaborative Robots

Abstract: This Technical Specification specifies safety requirements for collaborative industrial robot systems and the work environment, and supplements the requirements and guidance on collaborative industrial robot operation given in ISO 10218-1 and ISO 10218-2 [ANSI/RIA R15.06-2012]. This Technical Specification applies to industrial robot systems as described in ISO 10218-1 and ISO 10218-2 [ANSI/RIA

R15.06-2012]. It does not apply to non-industrial robots, although the safety principles presented can be useful to other areas of robotics.

Document Type: Report

 URL: <https://webstore.ansi.org/Standards/RIA/RIATRR156062016>

 Published: Q4 2016

Title: Applicability Of ANSI/RIA R15.06-2012 For Existing Industrial Robot Applications

Abstract: TR 506 explains how to take the 2012 R15.06 standard into account for existing robot systems, rather than the all-new robot installation that is the primary topic of the 2012 R15.06. The TR 506 document as published in 2014 continues to be the current active version.

Document Type: Report

 URL: <https://webstore.ansi.org/Standards/RIA/RIATRR155062014>

 Published: Q2 2014

TM Forum

Title: AI Closed Loop Automation – Anomaly Detection and Resolution v2.1.0

Abstract:

Document Type: Report

 URL: <https://www.tmforum.org/resources/how-to-guide/ig1219-ai-closed-loop-automation-anomaly-detection-and-resolution-v2-1-0/>

 Published: Q3 2021

COVR

Title: Test Exoskeleton for Single Axis Rotation Beyond Pre-Set Limits for Individual Patient Movement

Abstract: The purpose of the protocol is to validate the safety skill “limit range of movement” for an angular motion of a single joint of an exoskeleton or a restrained-type rehabilitation robot. The range of motion is measured using an electro-goniometer.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: <https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/EXO-LRM-1%20Test%20Exoskeleton%20for%20Single%20Axis%20Rotation%20Beyond%20Pre-Set%20Limits%20for%20Individual%20Patient%20Movement20210723.pdf>

Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test exoskeleton for maintaining proper alignment for hinge type joints

Abstract: This protocol describes a method for validating the safety skill “Maintain proper alignment” for joint axis alignment (both translational as well as rotational) for exoskeleton type rehabilitation robots as well as exoskeleton type robots used in other domains. This protocol uses an instrumented artificial limb, by which the joint angles, contact forces as well as the forces and torques in the joint can be determined, to validate the skill.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: <https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/EXO-MPA-1%20Test%20Exoskeleton%20for%20Maintaining%20Proper%20Alignment%20for%20hinge%20type%20joints20210824.pdf>

Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test Dynamic stability for Weight support systems

Abstract: The purpose of this protocol is to test the skill “dynamic stability” of (mobile) weight support systems (with gait following function) type RACA robots* by measurement. Its scope is limited to weight support systems in indoor applications. In this context, the objective is to protect users and bystanders from injuries caused by tilting of the weight support system. The validation of this protocol requires that the reader has access to an inclinometer, a winch and a suitable 1D force sensor for tension force measurements.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: <https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/WSU-DYS-1%20Dynamic%20Stability%20for%20Weight%20Support%20Systems-20211020.pdf>

Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test correct weight support Level – using crane

Abstract: This protocol can be used to validate the weight support level for Weight Support Systems used in the healthcare domain, where the amount of weight support can be varied by a therapist according to the need for the therapy of a subject.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: <https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/WSU-LRE-2%20Validate%20Correct%20Support%20Value%20-%20using%20crane.pdf>

Published: Q4 2021

Title: Test Limit Restraining Energy for Upper Limb Exoskeleton Type RACA Robots

Abstract: This protocol is to be used to test the restraining energy that can be applied to a human subject during use of an exoskeleton used for upper limb support. This protocol is both aimed at exoskeletons used in the medical domain as well as at exoskeletons used in the industrial, logistic or agricultural domain.

Document Type: Recommended Practice

URL: <https://covrfilestorage.blob.core.windows.net/documents/protocols/EXO-LRE-2%20Test%20Limit%20Restraining%20Energy%20for%20Upper%20Extremity%20Exoskeleton.pdf>

Published: Q4 2021

Title: Artificial Intelligence and future directions for ETSI

Abstract: Discusses Robotics in the scope of Health and Societal Applications of AI

Document Type: Landscape

URL: https://www.etsi.org/images/files/ETSIWhitePapers/etsi_wp34_Artificial_Intelligence_and_future_directions_for_ETSI.pdf

Published: Q2 2020

IEC 62 SC 62D

Title: Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-77: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of robotically assisted surgical equipment

Abstract: IEC 80601-2-77:2019 applies to the BASIC SAFETY and ESSENTIAL PERFORMANCE of ROBOTICALLY ASSISTED SURGICAL EQUIPMENT (RASE) and ROBOTICALLY ASSISTED SURGICAL SYSTEMS (RASS), referred to as ME EQUIPMENT and ME SYSTEMS together with their INTERACTION CONDITIONS and INTERFACE CONDITIONS.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://webstore.iec.ch/publication/29933>

Published: Q3 2019

IEEE

Title: Standard for an Architectural Framework for the Internet of Things (IoT)

Abstract: Self-management of health, with decision-making processes(cognitive and robotics)

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://standards.ieee.org/project/index.html>

Published: Q4 2018

Title: Medical electrical equipment — Part 4-1: Guidance and interpretation — Medical electrical equipment and medical electrical systems employing a degree of autonomy

Abstract: IEC TR 60601-4-1:2017(E) is intended to help a manufacturer through the key decisions and steps to be taken to perform a detailed risk management and usability engineering processes for medical electrical equipment or a medical electrical system, hereafter referred to as MEE or MES, employing a degree of autonomy (DOA). This document provides a definition of DOA of MEE or MES and a medical robot, and also provides guidance on: - methodologies to perform the risk management process and usability engineering for an MEE or MES with a DOA; - considerations of basic safety and essential performance for an MEE and MES with a DOA; and - identifying the use of DOA, and similar concepts in existing ISO/IEC standards dealing with MEE or MES with the goal to facilitate alignment of standards by consistent use of the concept of DOA; and - distinguishing between medical robots, and other MEE and MES. Unless specified otherwise, this document considers MEE and MES together.

The manufacturer of an MEE or MES with a DOA is expected to design and manufacture an MEE or MES that fulfils its intended use and does not have unacceptable risk throughout its life-cycle. This document provides guidance to help the manufacturer in complying with the requirements of IEC 60601-1:2005 and IEC 60601-1:2005/AMD1:2012 for MEE and MES with DOA. The document is also intended as guidance for future standard writers. There are no prerequisites to this document.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/70755.html?browse=tc>

Published: Q2 2017

Title: Robotics — Application of ISO 13482 — Part 2: Application guidelines

Abstract: This document provides guidance on the use of ISO 13482 and is intended to facilitate the design of personal care robots in conformity with ISO 13482. Additional guidance is provided for users with limited experience of risk assessment and risk reduction. This document provides clarification and guidance on new terms and safety requirements introduced to allow close human-robot interaction and human-robot contact in personal care robot applications, including mobile servant robots, physical assistant robots and person carrier robots. This document considers the application of ISO 13482 to all service robots and includes related examples.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/71627.html>

Published: Q1 2019

Title: Robotics — Test methods for Exoskeleton-type Walking RACA Robot

Abstract: This document is to establish a test method for exoskeleton-type WALKING RACA ROBOT which is

intended to move from one location to another, by making reciprocating motion having intermittent contact with the travel surface.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/81161.html>

Published:

Title: Robotics — Modularity for service robots — Part 202: Information model for software modules

Abstract: This document complies with the ISO 22166-1 and CD 22166-201 family standards providing requirements and guidelines on specifications on modularity for service robots; in this context the document presents requirements and guidelines for an information model for software modules of service robots, where the information model relates to interoperability, reusability, and composability of software modules. In particular, the document focuses on interfaces, properties, composition, and execution-specific information, which are related to software modules.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/84589.html?browse=tc>

Published:

VDE/DKE

Title: Safety of household and similar appliances

Part 2-107: Particular requirements for robotic battery powered electrical lawnmowers;

Abstract: The European Standard EN 50636-2-107:2015 specifies safety requirements and their verification for the design and construction of robotic battery powered electrical rotary lawnmowers and their peripherals with the rated voltage of the battery being not more than 75 V d.c. charged by mains electrical and/or alternative energies, e.g. solar power.

This amendment was developed to align the current standard EN 50636-2-107:2015 with the major changes from IEC 60335-2-107:2017 +A1 :2020.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.vde-verlag.de/standards/1701598/e-din-en-50636-2-107-a3-vde-0700-107-a3-2021-04.html>

Published: Q2 2021

Title: Cleaning robots for household use

Abstract: This standard is applicable to dry cleaning robots for household use in or under conditions similar to those in households.

The purpose of this standard is to specify the essential performance characteristics of dry cleaning robots and to describe methods for measuring these characteristics.

This standard is neither concerned with safety nor with performance requirements.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.vde-verlag.de/standards/0700886/din-en-62929-vde-0705-2929-2015-05.html>

Published: Q2 2015

ETSI

Title: SmartM2M; Use cases for cross-domain data usability of IoT devices

Abstract: Scope of document is to identify, select and describe use cases where the IoT data and services require data usability specifications for machines consuming data for AI (for example machine learning). Enabling data usability with AI approach will also be considered. It includes Use Cases pertaining to Robots

Document Type: Report

URL: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_tr/103700_103799/103778/01.01.01_60/tr_103778v010101p.pdf

Published: Q4 2021

ISO TC 135

Title: Non-destructive testing — Robotic ultrasonic test systems — General requirements

Abstract: This document specifies the necessary system hardware components, the characteristics, the component requirements and conditions for the application of robotic ultrasonic test systems.

This document specifies the general requirements and acceptance criteria for robotic ultrasonic test systems.

This document is applicable to robotic ultrasonic test systems composed of one or more robot(s).

This document is applicable to conventional straight beam probes and immersion technique.

This document is also applicable for phased array probes but then additional tests can be necessary.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/79135.html>

Published:

Title: Robotics — Modularity for service robots — Part 1: General requirements

Abstract: This document presents requirements and guidelines on the specification of modular frameworks, on open modular design and on the integration of modules for realising service robots in various environments, including personal and professional sectors.

The document is targeted at the following user groups:

- ▷ modular service robot framework developers who specify performance frameworks in an unambiguous way;
- ▷ module designers and/or manufacturers who supply end users or robot integrators;
- ▷ service robot integrators who choose applicable modules for building a modular system.

This document includes guidelines on how to apply existing safety and security standards to service robot modules.

This document is not a safety standard.

This document applies specifically to service robots, although the modularity principles presented in this document can be utilized by framework developers, module manufacturers, and module integrators from other fields not necessarily restricted to robotics

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/72715.html>

Published: Q1 2021

Title: Requirements and architecture for indoor conversational robot systems

Abstract: Describes the requirements and architecture for an indoor conversational robot system. This Recommendation defines different functions to support indoor conversational robot systems.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.itu.int/ITU-T/recommendations/rec.aspx?rec=13916&lang=en>

Published: Q2 2019

Title: VCIO based description of systems for AI trustworthiness characterisation

Abstract: This VDE SPEC provides a way to describe certain socio–technical characteristics of systems and applications that incorporate artificial intelligence techniques and methods. The scope of application refers to products for which a particularly demanding level of trust is desired or required. By applying the VCIO model explained in this standard, it is possible to describe whether an AI product adheres to specific values and can be trusted. This standard can therefore e.g., form the basis for attaching a trust label to a product.

Document Type: Standard_Specification

URL: <https://www.vde.com/resource/blob/2242194/a24b13db01773747e6b7bba4ce20ea60/vcio-based-description-of-systems-for-ai-trustworthiness-characterisationvde-spec-90012-v1-0--en--data.pdf>

Published: Q2 2022

Standards and gaps in “Knowledge, Tasks and Maps Representations for Robotics” and “Functional Safety for Robotics”

Knowledge, Tasks and Maps Representations for Robotics

Humans expect that modern robots operate in close cooperation with humans and other robotic agents, not only in factories, but also in environments of human daily life, e.g., homes, crowded spaces, and so on. The aimed cooperation is not only within close physical contact with humans, where safety standards do exist and are well known by the industry. In recent decades, robot's applications to help humans in daily activities have increased. Not only at people's homes, but also in the healthcare, public spaces, environments. This fact demanded from the robotics industry novel technical developments, both in hardware and software, and its application in real world environments.

The application of artificial intelligence to robotics plays a decisive role in this evolution, where both scientific areas performed a back-to-back effort to push robots with adequate capabilities to work closer and with humans in industrial and/or daily life tasks. The above mentioned and still ongoing rapid development of artificial intelligent technology with robotic technology demands both sophisticated and standardized knowledge representation towards, e.g., interoperability between the immense technologies that are required for intelligent robots. In this sense, novel standards have been recently published within the IEEE. The first standard was the IEEE Std 1872-2015, where a Core Ontology for Robotics and Automation (CORA) was developed, that covered the main concepts and relations in the robotics field. The aim of the standard is to diminish the ambiguity and inconsistencies in the robotics domain knowledge. Moreover, the concepts and its relations are written in a machine-readable format for both humans and machines to understand each other's, within its interactions.

Follow-up work over CORA was recently published in the IEEE Std 1872.2, Autonomous Robots (AuR) Ontology, that uses standardized high-level descriptions of the environment, robot behaviors, and interactions with the environment and other agents, including human beings. Following this direction, the working group 1872.3 envisions applying such concepts to reasoning in the multiple robots scenario.

Regarding the environment in which the robots operate, significant efforts are presented in the IEEE Std 1873-2015, for Robot Map Data Representation for Navigation, by providing data models and data formats for two-dimensional (2D) metric and topological maps. This work is evolving in two separate IEEE working groups, to develop standards for 3D Map Data Representation, and Semantic Maps.

The knowledge of the environment, of the robots and how they evolve during tasks executions, needs to be standardized for a smooth and proper interoperability of the agents involved in robotic tasks. Moreover, task definitions need to be properly and unambiguously defined for real world scenarios, where humans, robots and other physical or information agents cooperate. This fact is mandatory to achieve an adequate verification and assessment of the outcomes of the robotic tasks to be performed. The IEEE 1872.1.1 working group envisions developing a guide for practical implementation of the specifications of a robotic task (IEEE Std 1871.1-2024) in a machine-readable format.

As stated previously, human-robot interactions (HRI) play a decisive role in modern robots. As such, practitioners and users of human-robot interaction technologies require a common terminology, i.e., a set relevant to human-robot interaction in service, social, education, industrial, and research robotic applications. Moreover, adequate recommended practices are to be developed for human-subject experiments in human-robot interaction research. These are the goals of the IEEE working groups P3107 and 3108, to develop a standard and a recommended practice.

A suitable risk assessment could be done as per Annex A of ISO 13849:2006 but since 2016 R15.306 has been available as a robot-specific risk assessment methodology.

Also available since 2016 is ISO/TS 15066. This technical specification is referenced from ISO 10218-1 and ISO 10218-2 and gives additional guidance for “collaborative robots” where “a robot system and people share the same workspace”. One of the key topics in ISO/TS 15066 is PFL (Power and force limiting). In this mode of operation physical contact between the robot and the operator is expected either deliberately or inadvertently. Risk reduction is achieved through inherently safe design (e.g., removal of pinch points or the use of padding) or using safety functions. There are standards that describe SSM (speed and separation monitoring) and these robots can operate much faster than for PFL when nobody is present and slow as humans approach before stopping or entering PFL mode as the distance reduces further. It’s all about productivity on the factory floor and in some cases that might still require keeping the robots in their cages.

Another class of robots includes mobile robots, sometimes referred to as mobots, a term to match robots and cobots. Types of mobots include AGV (automated guided vehicles), AMR (automated mobile robots), industrial trucks, IMR (industrial mobile robots), AIV (automated intelligent vehicles) and several more manufacturer specific terms. Some of these follow a fixed path marked on the floor but the newer and more flexible ones can find their way from A to B working their way around obstacles using machine vision. These robots are having a big impact in warehouses around the world delivering unrivalled efficiencies. If mounted with an arm (better called a manipulator) these robots merge the cobot and robot requirements and also because they are mobile involve new functional safety requirements related to lithium-ion batteries, fleet management and communications. Typically, the mobot standards find PL d or SIL 2 sufficient for the safety but a risk assessment is required for each application. Many of these robots seem to be assembled from modules and the ISO 22166 series of standards is under development to give guidance.

Previously robots navigated and kept humans at a distance using laser scanners but since 2018 the IEC 61496-3 revision allows the 3D TOF (a type of camera where the picture represents distance). Now with a point cloud to play with the use of AI becomes attractive and the proposed ISO TR 5469 will hopefully give functional safety guidance in this area. However, it may be that safety will still be assured using laser scanners or 3D cameras.

In the nonindustrial world mobots are attractive for last mile deliveries of food or packages with some of the same challenges as mobots used in industrial environments but with additional challenges because they must interact with the public. Typically, workers on a factory floor are adults in good health and with proper training. In the real world there are children, people in wheelchairs, blind people and nobody has any training in dealing with robots.

Another class of robots are those used to help people in their homes, and these are covered by ISO 13482. While everybody thinks of humanoid robots some of these can be a smart speaker on wheels connected to a home automation system, which may or may not be compliant to the IEC 63168 series, or a tray on wheels. While a tray on wheels might seem simple the reviews from those who can’t walk and carry a cup of tea have been very positive for such robots. Eventually they may be able to cook and clean surfaces but as seen by the popularity of robot lawn mowers it is more likely that in the short term, they will sneak slowly into our lives to carry out specific and limited applications.

The main international consensus standards group dealing with robotics is ISO TC 299 WG 6. This group is organized as below:

- ▷ ISO/TC 299/WG 1 – vocabulary and characteristics
- ▷ ISO/TC 299/WG 2 – Personal care robot safety
- ▷ ISO/TC 299/WG 3 – Industrial safety
- ▷ ISO/TC 299/WG 4 – Service robots
- ▷ ISO/TC 299/WG 5 – Medical robot safety
- ▷ ISO/TC 299/WG 6 – Modularity for service robots
- ▷ ISO/TC 299/WG 7 - Management system for service robots
- ▷ ISO/TC 299/WG 8 - Validation methods for collaborative applications

■ References

- [1] ETSI TS 103 195-2 (published by ETSI in May 2018): Autonomic network engineering for the self-managing Future Internet (AFI); Generic Autonomic Network Architecture; Part 2: An Architectural Reference Model for Autonomic Networking, Cognitive Networking and Self-Management
- [2] IEEE NGR (International Network Generations Roadmap) 2022/2023 EDITION; IEEE INGR (International Network Generations Roadmap)/Future Networks, Standardization Building Blocks (SBB) Roadmap Chapter
- [3] IEEE NGR (International Network Generations Roadmap) 2022/2023/2024 EDITION; IEEE INGR (International Network Generations Roadmap)/Future Networks, Systems Optimization Roadmap Chapter
- [4] White Paper No.4 of the ETSI 5G PoC: ETSI GANA as Multi-Layer Artificial Intelligence (AI) Framework for Implementing AI Models for Autonomic Management & Control (AMC) of Networks and Services; and Intent-Based Networking (IBN) via GANA Knowledge Planes (KPs): https://intwiki.etsi.org/index.php?title=Accepted_PoC_proposals
- [5] ETSI TR 103 747 (published by ETSI in 2021): Core Network and Interoperability Testing (INT/WG AFI); Federated GANA Knowledge Planes (KPs) for Multi-Domain Autonomic Management & Control (AMC) of Slices in the NGMN® 5G End-to-End Architecture Framework
- [6] ETSI White Paper No. 56: Unlocking Digital Transformation with Autonomous Networks: ETSI perspectives and major achievements, First edition – March 2023
- [7] Abdelaali Chaoub, Aarne Mämmelä, Pedro Martinez-Julia, Ranganai Chaparadza, et al: Hybrid Self-Organizing Networks: Evolution, Standardization Trends, and a 6G Architecture Vision: IEEE Communications Standards Magazine; March 2023; DOI: 10.1109/MCOMSTD.0002.2200049

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